

Electronic, didactic and innovative platform for learning based on multimedia assets

e-DIPLOMA

Funded by
the European Union

Project website, Logo, and Social network accounts

Version 1.4 28 October 2022

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HISTORY OF CHANGES			
Version*	Publication date	Beneficiaries	Changes
V1.0	19.10.2022	FUE-UJI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Initial version of Deliverable Owner
V1.2	21.10.2022	UJI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Version including suggestions of WP Contributors
V1.3	26.10.2022	CSI, ARIS FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pre-final version reviewed by Internal Reviewers
V1.4	28.10.2022	UJI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Final version approved by Project Coordinator

(*) According to the section "Review and Submission of Deliverables" of the Project Handbook

1. Technical References

Project Number	101061424
Project Acronym	e-DIPLOMA
Project Title	Electronic, Didactic and Innovative Platform for Learning based On Multimedia Assets
Granting Authority	European Research Executive Agency (REA)
Call	HORIZON-CL2-2021-TRANSFORMATIONS-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL2-2021-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-05
Type of the Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Duration	1 September 2022 – 31 August 2025 (36 months)
Entry into force of the Grant	1 September 2022
Project Coordinator	Inmaculada Remolar Quintana

Deliverable No.	D8.2: Project Website, Logo and Social Networks accounts
Work Package	WP8: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan
Task	T8.2: Project Website, Logo and Social Networks accounts
Dissemination level*	PU- Public
Lead beneficiary	Universitat Jaume I (UJI)
PIC of the Lead beneficiary	999882985
Contributing beneficiary/ies	Fundación Universitat Jaume I-Empresa (FUE-UJI)
PIC of the Contributing beneficiary/ies	FUE-UJI: 942762983
Due date of deliverable	30 October 2022
Actual submission date	28 October 2022

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3. Project Website

To host the project main information and aiming to contribute to the dissemination and communication of the project, it has been bought the following domain:

<https://e-diplomaproject.eu/>.

The e-DIPLOMA webpage, hosted using a secure domain, will be a key instrument for supporting the dissemination of the research results, providing access to deliverables and presentation material that will support project’s promotion.

In terms of the structure, it is necessary to take into account that it is a dynamic website capable of adapting to the different phases and needs of the project over time, currently the webpage is divided in five different sections, each of which includes information about one key aspect of the project, all of them are permanently accessible through the superior menu bar which also includes funding information and project logo (Figure 1). Each of the five sections is described below.

Figure 1. Website menu bar.

- **HOME** (Figure 2): The first section shown to the user is the homepage, which is used to introduce the main aspects of the project such as the logotype, the project motto and its objectives and phases.

Figure 2. Home section of the web page.

- **PROJECT** (Figure 3): This section extends the information about the project, its framework, and fields of knowledge, starting point, the innovation that will be established in the field of e-learning by the end of the project and its goals and values. This section uses vocabulary and expressions easy to understand for the general public and users without scientific background in order to contribute to the communication tasks.

Figure 3. Project section of the web page.

- **PARTNERS** (Figure 4): This section provides information on the project’s partners through their logos and a brief description of the institution and its activities. In addition, this section also includes the affiliated entity figure.

Figure 4. Partners section of the web page.

- **RESULTS** (Figure 5): This section is oriented to a scientific public, researchers and entities related to the project. Here, the user can find a list of all the work packages, a brief description of each of them and the deliverables expected to submit within the project lifetime. It is also specified to each of the deliverables if the information provided is public or sensitive to the general society.

WORK PACKAGES				
WP1: Project management				
The objective of WP1 is to ensure the efficiency of the project governance. It includes coordinating, monitoring, and structuring all project activities.				
Number	Title	Lead	Dissemination Level	Release Date
D1.1	Project Handbook (PH)	UJI	Confidential	31 Oct 2022
D1.2	Kick off and semi-annual project meeting minutes	UJI	Confidential	31 Aug 2025
D1.3	Data Management Plan	CSI	Public	28 Feb 2023
WP2: Focused view on European current situation of elearning and co-creation of educational practices with emerging technologies				
It includes the e-learning ecosystem analysis, the study of remote e-learning in teacher training and the preparation of a toolbox of best practices.				

Figure 5. Results section of the web page.

- **CONTACT** (Figure 6): The last section included in the top menu bar is Contact, in which appears a contact form to help users to get in touch with the project’s organizers as well as an interactive map showing where the project office is located within the UJI campus. All the social media profiles and linked to the website.

Contact us!

Name *

First Last

Email *

Comment or Message

Submit

Figure 6. Contact section of the web page.

- **SITEMAP** (Figure 7). In addition, and with the purpose of improving the user experience once the audience has reached the website, we have developed a dynamic version of the logotype consisting of an animation of the pixels that move slowly to become the diploma. As a footer and according to the article 17.3 of the GA we have included the disclaimer text.

Figure 7. Sitemap.

4. Logo

With the purpose to contribute to the communication and dissemination of the project, it has been developed a visual identity strategy including aspects such as the logotype, design and implementation, the colour palette or typography.

Figure 8. e-DIPLOMA logo.

- **e-DIPLOMA LOGOTYPE** (Figure 8). The core idea behind the logotype is to integrate both, the traditional and the most innovative education. To achieve this, we choose a diploma as the emblematic representation of traditional education and integrated it with pixels that dissolve and represent the Virtual Reality environment.

- COLOUR PALETTE** (Figure 9). To choose the colour palette of the project visual identity, we have taken into account some studies (e.g. 99 designs technology) that indicate blue, black, white and red as the colours people relate more with the technology field.

Figure 9. 99 designs technology

For that reason, the final colours selected to build up e-DIPLOMA’s visual identity are Pantone (Figure 10) 1645C R: 255 / G: 109 / B: 66 HTML: #FF6D42 and Pantone 2767C R: 24 / G: 43 / B: 73 HTML: #182B49.

Figure 10. 99 Pantone

- **FINAL LOGOTYPE** (Figure 11): According to the article 17 of the GA we have added the European emblem next to the logotype which must be displayed in any publication or output. The logotype must not be depicted by itself without the European emblem.

Figure 11. e-DIPLOMA & European Union Logotypes

5. Social network accounts

According to what was stated in the e-DIPLOMA form, the [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#) and [Youtube](#) accounts have been created with fully identity of the project. Different strategies are being applied to each channel to engage many audiences.

Twitter (Figure 12) strategy will combine both, communication, and dissemination messages to reach a wider audience including researchers, organizations, students and businesses.

Figure 12. e-DIPLOMA Twitter

LinkedIn (Figure 13) strategy will be more oriented to reach potential stakeholders and investors.

Figure 13. e-DIPLOMA LinkedIn

Facebook (Figure 14) strategy will focus mainly on communication messages and having students, parents, and educative institutions as a target.

Figure 14. e-DIPLOMA Facebook

Finally, The EU emblem and the disclaimer have been applied in every communication and dissemination channel. On the website and the presentation templates, it has been incorporated as mentioned in the Article 17 – Communication, Dissemination and Visibility of the General Model Grant Agreement EIC Accelerator Contract with the following text:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA) can be held responsible for them.”

In addition, we have included a disclaimer on social media accounts with the following text:

“All related publications and opinions expressed reflect only the views of the project owner and do not reflect necessarily those of the European Union or the Research Executive Agency.”

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